
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AS A DRIVER OF ENHANCED EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN GUARANTEE TRUST BANK, UYO

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The study was conducted to assess the relationship between social skill which is an aspect of Emotional Intelligence and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Survey research design was employed. Population of the study was 92. The entire population was used as the sample size owing to its small nature. Primary and secondary sources of data were employed for the study. Modified Likert scale was used as the instrument for collecting data and they were administered to the respondents in their respective offices. Pearson product moment correlation statistical too, was used in testing the studied hypothesis. Findings revealed an R-value of 0.68 which is greater than the critical R-value of 0.217. It was therefore concluded that social skill significantly relates to employees’ performance in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Nigeria. As recommendation, management of Guarantee Trust Bank should organise get-together, parties, picnics and other social events to enable their employees acquire social skill.</p>	<p>Emotional Intelligence, Social skills, Employees’ Performance</p>

Introduction

Emotional intelligence (EI) has become a very important topic in management and education in the last decade, especially in regard to how it affects today’s employees, managers and leaders. In recent times, employers have incorporated emotional intelligence tests in their interviews, perhaps on the assumption that, those high in emotional intelligence would make better employees, leaders and co-workers (Cherry, 2018). It is also assumed that high emotional intelligence can help one navigate the social complexities of the workplace, lead and motivate others and excel in one’s career. In fact, when it comes to gauging important job candidates, many companies now rate emotional intelligence as important as technical abilities and employ emotional quotient (EQ) testing before hiring. According to Scuderi (2014) in any human endeavour which includes working in organisation, people or employees that are believed to be highly intelligent may not succeed or perform better than those who are believed to be less intelligent. The difference between the effectiveness and efficiency in performances may be hinged on abilities, which according to Scuderi (2014) may be as a result of employee’s emotions.

Emotions, according to Salovey *et al.* (2007) are organised responses crossing the physiological, cognitive, motivational and exponential sub-systems of the brain. Goleman (2005) defined emotions as guiding forces that help humans in facing predicaments and tasks that one's intelligence alone cannot handle. The author went further to state that, for better or worse, intelligence can come to nothing when emotion holds sway; that is, when employee's emotional states such as anger, anxiety, depression, sorrow, excitement among others control or determine the employee's job performance. In other words, employees need to act based on their emotional intelligence. This will guide their actions, inactions and reactions to situations and people. Cherry (2020) viewed emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotions. Goleman (2005) described emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive, appraise and express emotions accurately and adaptively and the ability to regulate emotions in oneself and in others. Goleman (1998) categorised emotional intelligence as encompassing self-awareness, selfregulation, motivation, empathy and social skill. This study is concerned with the social skill.

Social skill refers to managing relationships to move people in the desired direction (Goleman, 2005). It refers to interacting well with other people. It also involves applying an understanding of the emotions of ourselves and others to communicate and interact with others on a day-to-day basis. It further means managing relationships to get along with others. Social skill means the ability of employees to relate well with customers and co-workers both within and outside the work environment. It also denotes employees' ability to hold and sustain relationships with customers and co-workers. It further entails the various skills displayed by employees towards developing a healthy relationship within and outside the organization. Social skill is essential for the development of positive, cordial and effective relationship with customers, and co-workers and to interact with team members. It allows people to interact socially with one another and to successfully navigate social situations. Those with high EQs generally have higher than average social skills and are able to effectively pursue their goals and get the outcomes they want when interacting with others (Cherry, 2018).

Employees who are equipped with social skills would be able to develop and manage relationships, and would love to be involved in joint problem solving. They have the ability to communicate with others respectfully and how to tactically influence their perceptions. They also have active listening skills and are ever ready to be involved in group or team work. They are ever excited to attend colleagues' get together, parties, picnics and other social events. They do not hesitate to give their phone numbers to customers and colleagues, and do not hesitate to respond to chats, text and e-mail messages. They know the names of almost all their colleagues and do not feel reluctant to visit their colleagues either in the office or at home to strengthen the bond of unity and love. Such gestures are invaluable in team work or joint problem solving.

Employees with social skills would be able to maintain a lasting relationship with colleagues, despite their limitations or diversities. Such employees would be cherished by the majority of customers and colleagues since they would be able to make others feel important. With social skill, employees would be able to handle conflict with co-workers, and address them with diplomacy. These employees would maintain cordial relationship with them despite their individual differences. These employees would also employ dialogue in resolving conflicts in the organization and work hard to reconcile with aggrieved colleagues, which in no small measure would lead to superior job performance. According to Imagha *et al.* (2024), the performance of employees plays a crucial role in determining the overall success of an organisation. Performance can be described as the manner in which an individual carries out their job, with effectiveness serving as the criterion by which it is evaluated (Casio in Imagha *et al.*,2024).

Statement of the Problem

The theory of emotional intelligence is enjoying considerable successful applications in many domains. It is seen as being essential to effective and efficient job performance in organisations. Recently, employers have incorporated emotional intelligence tests in interviews, perhaps on the assumption that those who are high in emotional intelligence would make better employees, leaders and co-workers in the organisations. Proponents and experts of emotional intelligence argue that intelligent quotient (IQ) has limited role in employees, managers and leaders' success, while emotional intelligence enables them to achieve more success. As a result, there has been increased attention on the concept of emotional intelligence by researchers, bankers, medical professionals, transporters, management consultancy firms, recruitment agencies, management practitioners, psychologists and especially educationists.

Several studies conducted in America, Europe, Asia and in some parts of Africa and Nigeria have shown that emotional intelligence leads to effective job performance. Studies have also shown that people with high EI have greater mental health, academic success, job performance and leadership skills. However, despite these great successes recorded in these parts of the world and in transport, health and education sector, there is paucity of reports and literature on emotional intelligence and employees' job performance in the banking sector in South-South, Nigeria.

Furthermore, the researcher observed that, some bank employees could not regulate or control their emotions or negative impulses especially when dealing with some egoistic customers as well as with some unfriendly, high-handed and domineering co-workers and leaders, which may be as a result of lack of emotional intelligence skills. This was felt or adjudged to have some adverse or negative impacts on their job performance. Therefore, this study sought to assess the influence of social skill on the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to assess the influence of emotional intelligence on the performance of employees of Guarantee Trust Bank in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study sought to examine the relationship between social skills and the performance of employees of Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question

i. What relationship exists between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Literature Review Concept of Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is a set of cognitive and non-cognitive competencies, skills and abilities, directly and essentially connected to the behaviours and actions of everyone in every field, including the actions of educationists, public administrators, policy-makers, managers and leaders at any level of the organisation bureaucracy (Faltas, 2017). It enhances and endorses the type of human behaviour that promotes fairness, social justice, social balance, leadership, trust, respect, motivation, growth and excellence. It also improves and helps

us to build stronger relationships, influencing our senses, from the way we perceive to the way we think about the world around us (Faltas, 2017).

Emotional intelligence concerns the ability to carry out accurate reasoning about emotions and the ability to use emotions and emotional knowledge to enhance thought (Mayer *et al.*, 2008). It is all about identifying emotions in ourselves and others, relating to others and communicating about our feelings (Cherry, 2018). It is what business educators use when they empathise with coworkers and students, have deep conversations about their relationships with others, and attempt to manage unruly or distraught students. It allows business educators to connect with others, understand themselves better and live a more authentic, healthy and happy life.

According to Segal *et al.* (2019) emotional intelligence (otherwise known as emotional quotient or EQ) is the ability to understand, use and manage one's own emotions in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathise with others, overcome challenges and defuse conflict. Emotional intelligence helps employees to connect with their feelings, turn intention into action, and make informed decisions about what matters most to them. High emotional intelligence can help employees navigate social complexities of the workplace, lead and motivate others and excel in their career. In fact, when it comes to gauging important job candidates, many companies now rate emotional intelligence as important as technical abilities and employ EQ testing before hiring (Segal *et al.*, 2019).

Emotional intelligence might be defined as the set of skills people use to read, understand and react effectively to emotional signals sent by others and oneself (Srivastava, 2013). These skills are; empathy, problem-solving, optimism and self-awareness, and they allow or help people to reflect, react to, and understand various environmental situations. According to Serrat (2017) emotional intelligence describes the ability, capacity, skill or self-perceived ability to identify, assess, and manage the emotions of oneself, of others and of groups. People who possess a high degree of emotional intelligence know themselves very well and are also able to sense the emotions of others. They are affable, resilient and optimistic.

Social Skill and Employees' Performance

Social skill is also known as relationship management. This is the ability of employees to relate well with customers and co-workers within and outside the work environment. It also means employees' ability to hold and sustain relationship with other employees, customers and management. Being able to interact well with others is another important aspect of emotional intelligence. True emotional understanding involves more than just understanding one's own emotions and that of others. One also needs to be able to put this information to work in one's daily interactions and communications (Cherry, 2020). Cherry stressed that, in professional settings managers benefit by being able to build relationships and connections with employees. Employees benefit from being able to develop a strong rapport with leaders and co-workers. Employees can also benefit from being able to develop a strong rapport with co-workers and customers. Important social skills include active listening, verbal communication skills, nonverbal communication skills, leadership and persuasiveness (Cherry, 2020).

Social skills are the last piece of the EQ puzzle. These skills are what allow people to interact socially with one another and to successfully navigate social situations. Those with high EQs generally have higher than average social skills and are able to effectively pursue their goals and get the outcomes they want when interacting with others (Cherry, 2018). According to Cherry (2018) this component of EI refers to interacting well with other people. It involves applying an understanding of the emotions of ourselves and others to communicate and interact with others on a day to day basis. Different social skills include: active listening, verbal communication skills, non-verbal communication skills, leadership and developing rapport (Cherry, 2018a).

Social skill refers to learning how to effectively manage relationships and inspire others (Riopel, 2019). It is the ability to manage the emotions of others through emotional understanding and using this to build rapport and connect with people through skills such as active listening, verbal and non-verbal communication (Houston, 2019). Social skill refers to proficiency in managing and building networks (Ovans, 2015). Employees who do well in the social skill element of emotional intelligence are great communicators. They are as open to hearing bad news as good news and they are experts at getting their team to supporting them and be excited about a new mission or project.

Social skill is a set of emotional intelligence skills that help employees manage their interpersonal relationships and elicit certain reactions from them (Moore, 2019). It is the ability to develop and maintain good relationships, communicate clearly, inspire and influence others, work well in a team and manage conflict. It also refers to the ability to influence, coach and mentor others and resolve conflict effectively (Landry, 2019). Research shows that every unaddressed conflict can waste about eight hours of company time in gossip and other unproductive activities, putting a drain on resources and morale (Landry, 2019). Employees who want to keep happy teams need to have those tough conversations. In a recent survey by the Society for Human Resource Management, 72 percent of employees ranked respectful treatment of all employees at all levels as the top factor in job satisfaction (Landry, 2019).

Social skill or relationship management, according to Goleman (2015) concerns the skill or adeptness at inducing desirable responses in others. The relationship management cluster, according to Goleman contains six competencies, namely:

- a. developing others: sensing others' development needs and bolstering their abilities;
- b. inspirational leadership: inspiring and guiding individuals and groups;
- c. change catalyst: initiating or managing change;
- d. influence: wielding effective tactics for persuasion;
- e. conflict management: negotiating and resolving disagreements and
- f. teamwork and collaboration: working with other toward shared goals. Creating group synergy in pursuing goals.

According to Goleman (2006) relationship management is the ability to inspire, influence and develop others while managing conflict. The relationship management domain as explained by Goleman (2006) contains competencies that have the most direct effect on interaction with other people. Social skill refers to managing relationships to move people in the desired direction (Goleman, 2005). Relationship management is especially important when it comes to fostering diversity and inclusion in the workplace. People who are skilled in managing relationships are better equipped to handle conflict drawing out all parties, helping others understand differing perspectives and common ideals that everyone can endorse (Goleman *et al.*, 2002). Individuals skilled in relationship management value teamwork and encourage an atmosphere that is friendly and safe, theorizing respect, helpfulness and co-operation (Goleman *et al.*, 2002). These competencies are critical for leading and job performance in a diverse organisation effectively (Morton, 2012).

Social skill refers to proficiency in managing relationships and building networks, and an ability to find common ground and build rapport. It includes effectiveness in leading change, persuasiveness and expertise building and leading teams (Goleman, 1999). Social skills are essential for the development of positive, cordial and effective relationship with other employees and the ability to interact with team members to deter conflict, be aware of, ease and dissipate underlying tensions that can accumulate and have a negative impact on working relationship

and project success. Team members need to be able to stimulate co-operation, collaboration and team work through well-developed social skills (Goleman, 1998). Goleman (1998) stressed that, there are eight competencies relating to social skills, namely:

- a. influence: wielding effective tactics for persuasion;
- b. communication: sending clear and convincing messages;
- c. leadership: inspiring and guiding groups and people;
- d. change catalyst: initiating or managing change;
- e. conflict management: negotiating and resolving disagreements;
- f. building bonds: nurturing instrumental relationships;
- g. collaboration and co-operation: working with others toward shared goals and
- h. team capabilities: creating group synergy in pursuing collective goals.

Social skills also called interpersonal skills are those skills employees and leaders use to interact and communicate with other people (Doyle, 2011). These skills include both verbal skills (the way one speaks to other people) and non-verbal skills (one's body language, gestures and eye contact). Doyle stressed that, social skills are important soft skills, that is, personal qualities (as opposed to professional hard skills acquired through education, training or job experience) that are key to interacting well with others. Doyle further stressed that, almost every job requires social skills. If one works with clients, one must listen attentively to their questions and concerns. If one is a manager, one would be called upon to motivate employees (Doyle, 2011). Similarly, if one is a business educator or teacher, one would be called upon to impart knowledge on the students effectively.

Social skill or relationship management is the ability to manage emotions in others (Orluwene and Wachukwu, 2014). It refers to a person's talent in managing relationship with others and building systems also called people skills. The set of social skills includes respect for others, mutual regard, commitment, openness, tolerance, empathy, negotiation, communication etc (Schuetz cited in Mohamad and Jais, 2015). It involves the ability of meeting each other's needs, relating to each other over time and exchanging information about one's feelings, thoughts and ideas. Social skills are effective in leading change, persuading others, building and leading teams (Goleman, 1995). It is also a very useful tool for resolving conflict in healthy, constructive ways thereby strengthening trust among people.

Relationship management manifests in handling emotions in relationships well and accurately reading social situations and networks, interacting smoothly, and using these skills to persuade and lead, negotiate and settle dispute for co-operation and team work (Ugoani *et al.*, 2015). Effective social skills consist of managing relationships in a way that benefits both the organisation and the employees. Employees who have good social skills are also good at managing change and resolving conflicts diplomatically. They are rarely satisfied with leaving things as they are, but they do not sit back and make everyone else do the work; they set an example with their behaviour. Research shows that social skill has direct impact on job performance and thus will enhance productivity in an organisation (Hua, 2019).

Social skills are important because they can help employees communicate more effectively and efficiently. It can also help them build, maintain and grow relationships with co-workers, and new contacts alike. Employees' interpersonal skills have a direct effect on their ability to interact and get along with others, build critical relationships and function as productive members of a team (Scher, 2013). Social skills are more than just being friendly. Goleman (2005) described them as friendliness with a purpose; meaning everyone is treated politely and

with respect, yet healthy relationships are then also used for personal and organisational benefits. Goleman argued that individuals that adopt these characteristics give themselves a far greater chance of being successful than individuals that do not.

Social skills can be seen as set of skills people use to interact and communicate with one another. They are based on the social norms of the society and they tell us what attitudes and behaviours are considered to be normal, acceptable and expected in a particular social situation (Patrick, 2008). Beheshtifar and Norozy (2013) defined social skill as the ability that produces behaviours that will positively reinforce and not produce behaviours that will be punished by others. Good social skills include both what is said during a social interaction and how it is said. When communicating with another person, the verbal content of the message, that is, the person's choice of words or phrases is important. How that message is communicated can be just as important as the message itself. A case in point, appropriate facial expressions, body language, eye contact and a good firm voice tone all help to communicate the message (Beheshtifar and Norozy, 2013).

Social skills are important in the workplace because they allow employees to interact with one another with predictability, so that they can more readily understand one another and be understood. Without an agreed upon social way of interacting, it is very hard to prevent misunderstandings. It is important for employees and leaders to be able to interact with clarity

(Patrick, 2008). Social skills also allow an individual the opportunity to express both negative and positive feeling in interpersonal situations without losing social reinforcement (Hersen and Bellack cited in Beheshtifar and Norozy, 2013). Strong social skill facilitates interpersonal interactions which can in turn lead to effective job performance (Beheshtifar and Norozy, 2013). Social skill has been theorised as a moderating variable that enhances employees' job performance (Hogan and Shelton cited in Beheshtifar and Norozy, 2013). In particular, Witt and Ferris (2003) found that social skill moderates the relationship between conscientiousness and job performance, such that the relationship was stronger for individuals with higher social skill.

Johnson and Johnson cited in Beheshtifar and Norozy (2013) listed six important outcomes of being socially skilled. The first desirable outcome is personal development and identity because most people's identity is created out of relationships with others. As a result of interacting with others, we have a better understanding of ourselves. Individuals who have few interpersonal skills have distorted relationship with others and tend to develop inaccurate and incomplete view of themselves. Social skills also tend to enhance "employability, productivity and career success," major skills required in the real world of work. The most important skills, especially for higher paying jobs, are getting others to co-operate, leading others, coping with complex situations and helping solve people's work related problems. Quality of life is another positive outcome of social skills because everybody needs good, close, and intimate relationship in life. Physical health is promoted also through positive and supportive relationships. Research has shown that high quality relationships are linked to longer lives and to quicker recovery from illness and injury. Research has also shown that psychological health is strongly influenced by positive and supportive relationship with others. An incapacity to establish and sustain positive relationships with others very often leads to anxiety, depression, frustration, alienation and loneliness. It has been proven that the ability to build positive relationships with others reduces psychological distress, while increasing autonomy, self-identity and self-esteem. The sixth important benefit that results from having social skills is the ability to cope with stress. Supportive relationships have been shown to decrease the number and severity of stressful events and to reduce anxiety. Such relationships help individuals cope with stress by providing caring information, resources, and feedback (Johnson and Johnson cited in Beheshtifar and Norozy, 2013).

Theoretical framework Mixed Theory of EI - Daniel Goleman (1998)

Goleman (1998) mixed theory focused on EI as a wide array of competencies and skills that drive leadership performance. EI competencies are not innate talents, but rather learned capabilities that must be worked on and can be developed to achieve outstanding performance. Goleman posited that individuals are born with a general emotional intelligence that determines their potential for learning emotional competencies.

The theory is described as mixed because the theorist re-conceptualised EI as a combination of trait and ability theory. Goleman (1998) developed the new theory because of the limitations and criticisms of the (1995) theory for not considering empathy as a separate domain. Empathy, which is an independent and indispensable skill in the discourse of EI was incorporated in the domain of social-awareness in the (1995) theory. This made the construct of empathy not fully explored in subsequent researches using Goleman's (1995) theory. However, Goleman's research over the years has allowed him to modify and re-categorise the domains of EI. The theorist currently asserts that, there are five main EI constructs:

- a. self-awareness: the ability to know one's emotions, strengths, weaknesses, drives, values and goals and recognise their impact on others while using gut feelings to guide decisions.
- b. self-regulation: involves controlling or redirecting one's disruptive emotions and impulses and adapting to changing circumstances.
- c. motivation: being aware of what motivates them.
- d. empathy: considering other people's feelings especially when making decisions.
- e. social skill: managing relationships to get along with others.

The relevance of the mixed theory to the present study is that, the theory considered the entire emotional intelligence variables or constructs outlined in the objectives of this study without variations in words usage. It also met the scientific criteria of a standard intelligence and was therefore adopted for the study.

Empirical Framework

Imagha and Ebieme (2024) conducted a study to examine the influence of self-regulation on job performance in Champion Brewery, Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Self-regulation was proxied into conscientious, transparency and optimism. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The total population of the employees working in the organization was Ninety 90 employees. 73 was arrived at as sample size, using Taro Yamene's formula for sample size determination. Both primary and secondary sources of data were employed for the study. Simple random sampling technique was adopted while the research instrument was a structure questionnaire. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used in analyzing the study. Findings revealed that conscientious had a high correlation value of $R = 0.647$ with an Unstandardized Coefficient Beta $\hat{\beta}^2=0.782$. Transparency showed an Unstandardized Coefficient Beta of $\hat{\beta}^2=0.688$ while optimism had an Unstandardized Coefficient Beta of $\hat{\beta}^2=0.646$. From the findings, it was concluded that self-regulation has a positive significant influence on employees's performance in Champion Brewery, Plc, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. As recommendations, management of Champion Brewery, Plc, Uyo should encourage employees to sharpen their conscientiousness and transparency skills as this will enable these employees to be in control of their emotions and ensure these emotions are effectively managed to avoid it affecting their work performance negatively. Also, optimism being a valuable psychological resource cannot be easily copied by the rivalry organisations, hence, assessing and developing optimism in employee will add to the competitive advantage of the organization, thus, it should be promoted.

Marengo and Chinyamurindi (2018) conducted a study on the influence of demographic variables on emotional intelligence among early career academics (ECAs) in South Africa. The quantitative approach was followed in conducting the study. Data were collected from a sample of 220 ECAs in a selected University in South Africa. A self-administered questionnaire was sent to the participants using survey monkey online data collection tool. Emotional intelligence was measured using the Schutte Emotional Intelligence Scale. The findings revealed a significant EI level differences based on the participants' ethnic background. However, no significant differences in EI levels could be found based on the respondents' gender, age and work experience. The relevance of this work to the present study is that it focused on emotional intelligence constructs and questionnaire for data collection just like the present study.

Ebieme *et al.* (2024) carried out a study to examine the influence of self-awareness on business educators' job performance in federal universities in south-south Nigeria. Self-awareness was decomposed into self-confidence, realistic self-assessment and self-depreciating sense of humor. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Population of the study was made up of 92 Business Educators in the five Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria. The entire population was used as the sample owing to its small nature. Both primary and secondary sources of data were employed for the study. Purposive sampling technique was adopted while the research instrument was a structure questionnaire. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were used in analyzing the study. Findings revealed that self-confidence had a moderated correlation value of $R=0.489$ with a standardized coefficient $\beta=0.538$. Realistic self-assessment showed a standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.737$ while self-depreciating sense of humor had a standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.961$. From the findings, it was concluded that self-awareness has a positive significant influence on business educators' in south-south, Nigeria. As recommendations, management of higher institutions should create more awareness about the importance of self-confidence to their business educators. Also, business educators should be encouraged to by managements of higher institutions to always have a realistic self-assessment. Management of universities in south-south Nigeria should endeavor to assess sense of humor when conducting the yearly appraisal via the employees' appraisal forms.

Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. This design was used since it aided the researcher to collect data directly from the respondents. Population of the study consisted of 92 staff (Personnel department) of Guarantee Trust Bank in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. By this small number, the entire population was used as the sample. This was informed by the assertion that, when the population is small, studying the entire population will provide higher validity and better understanding of the relationship between the variables in the study. This is in line with Osuala (2005) who opined that the entire population should be studied when the population is relatively small. Convenience sampling technique was adopted for this study. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire which was administered to the respondents in their respective offices. Scoring of the research instrument was done using modified Likert Scale. In the questionnaire, the respondents responded by indicating their degree of agreement or disagreement to each statement by ticking along the column provided. Scoring of the questionnaire was graded as follows: Strongly agree (SA) - 4; Agree (A) - 3; Disagree (D) - 2; Strongly disagree (SD) - 1; Undecided (UN) - 0. The descriptive and Pearson Product moment correlation statistics were used in the study. The descriptive statistics were percentage and frequency distribution tables which were used to capture respondents' demographic characteristics and frequency distribution of the responses on the study variables. Pearson Product moment correlation statistics was used to assess the relationship between the

independent variable and the dependent variable. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The researcher personally administered the instrument to the respondents during official hours. 79 out of 92 representing 85.9% copies administered were completed, returned and in useable form.

Data presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Research Question

i. What relationship exists between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Result of r-value of Pearson product moment correlation of the relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo (N=79)

Variables $\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	
$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Social skill	1190	18460	40153	0.68
Job performance	2630	88730		

Source: Field Work (2024).

The result presented in Table 1 shows the r-value of 0.68 which indicates a high positive relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. This result implies that there exists a high positive relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

H_{i1} : There is a significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 2: Pearson Product moment correlation of the relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo

Variables $\sum x$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value	Decision
$\sum y$	$\sum y^2$			
Social skill	1190	18460	40153	0.68
Job	2630	88730	performance	

*significant at .05 level, df = 77.

Source: Field Work (2024).

The result presented in Table 2 reveals that the calculated r-value of 0.68 is greater than the critical r-value of 0.217 at .05 level of significance and at 77 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of hypothesis five showed a significant relationship between social skill and the performance of employees in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo. Social skill is seen as an important element that influences job performance. Research by Hua (2019) revealed that social skill has direct impact on job performance and thus will enhance productivity in an organisation.

Social skill has been theorized as a moderating variable that enhances employees' job performance. In particular, Witt and Ferris (2003) found that social skill moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance such that the relationship was stronger for individuals with higher social skill. The finding of the study supports the work of Bahmanabadia and Jafari (2014) who found that there exists a meaningful relationship between social skill and job performance. It is noteworthy that social skill, as one of the components of EI indicated the greatest impact on performance.

The findings of the study underpin the work of Kumar and Kant (2012) who found that there exist significant positive relationship between social skill and professional development of secondary school teachers. It also underpins Gontur and Dekom's (2017) work which found that social skill was positively related to employees' job performance. It further underpins the work of Mohamad and Jais (2015) who found a significant correlation between social skill and job performance and satisfaction. The finding supports a study by Behbanani (2011) who found that there was a significant relationship between social skill and employees' capabilities.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, it was therefore concluded that social skill significantly relates to employees' performance in Guarantee Trust Bank, Uyo, Nigeria. As recommendation, management of Guarantee Trust Bank should organise get-together, parties, picnics and other social events to enable their employees acquire social skill. Moreover, employees who are introverts should be given special attention during training and re-training on EI.

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